

DEVELOPMENT OF MENTAL QUALITIES OF PRESCHOOL CHILDREN BY MEANS OF SPEECH CULTIVATION

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Annotation: The responsibility of providing early education to the youth of our country pre-school institutions currently operating in our country have taken over. In preschool institutions the form of knowledge transfer is training. In the process of training, the child's speech develops, the grammatical and phonetic edges in it are polished and, in addition to increasing the wealth of the language, the psychological and intellectual aspects develop.

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Historically formed content of human experience in verbal form generalized, while its statement and appropriation implies that speech is also involved in this process. Speech to the child man opens the way to all the achievements of his culture. In general, the person's and all the main psychic processes (perception, thinking, etc.) the formation of is also associated with the development of speech in a child. A special place in the psychical formation of a child is occupied by speech it makes it very important to know the conditions and factors that contribute to its development at different stages. With the development of speech, the issue of moving forces is intense even due to the fact that it occurs in the jumping style, it is important.

In the modern perception of speech ontogenesis, the development of Child speech is determined, on the one hand, by external influences, and on the other - by sudden occurrence, "self-actualization" is understood to be characterized by. By mastering passive speech of children it is decisive that they receive and say the initial

word the following three aspects, namely emotional connections, joint action the communication in the loop will depend on the communicative factor, which consists of a vowel connection.

All the achievements of the child in mastering the language system include fluent speech, which is considered as a meaningful, widely disseminated thought that provides communication. It has content, logic, and characterized by consistency. How fluent speech child language wealth considered an indicator of appropriation, it reflects the level of development of the child mentally, aesthetically, emotionally.

For the development of preschool education, do the following it will be necessary to increase:

- * prioritize qualified educator and pedagogical personnel preparation;
- * search and introduction of effective psychological and pedagogical methods of preschool education;
- * organizational, psychological upbringing of children in the family to school, pedagogical and methodological support;
- * modern educational and methodological manuals, technical means, creating toys and games and producing them;
- * spiritual and moral children of preschool age on the basis of the rich cultural and historical heritage of the people and universal values creating conditions for upbringing in terms;
 - for different types of preschool institutions selection of programs in different ways, preschool education provide qualified consultation service on all issues making it possible;
- * preschool and wellness institutions
 - developed the mechanism of support and development of the network targets tasks such as output.

As well as preschool education in the Republic of Uzbekistan the regulation places a special emphasis on preschool education and provides for the primary education of the preschool continuing education system it is considered a type of

"Education" of the Republic of Uzbekistan law "on", requirements of the National Training Program it is organized on the basis of.

Preschool education, until the child reaches the age of 6-7 years in the family and state and non-state, non-state preschool it is carried out in institutions.

The types of preschool are selected by the parents. The procedure for receiving children to a preschool educational institution, moving them from one institution to another, from the institution

discharge in public institutions in accordance with the procedure established by the Ministry of public education, non-state preschool education in institutions, on the other hand, it is determined by the Charter of the institution.

Which have disadvantages in mental and physical development the establishment of special preschools or groups for children is also specified in the regulation on preschool education.

As in every field, in the preschool system persons with relevant education, professional training and high moral qualities in preschool educational institutions they have the right to engage in pedagogical activity.

Educational Management Authority by public authorities training, retraining and professional development of pedagogical personnel, maintaining the quality of the profession at a competitive level will be provided.

Educational training of pedagogical personnel of preschool educational institutions the pedagogical task is determined by the Ministry of public education based on state requirements for the type of preschool educational institution. Advanced pedagogical and information technologies, specialists new programs recommended by, methodological manuals, provide conditions for the introduction of didactic materials.

Relationship of pedagogical personnel cooperation, democracy, respect, recognition of the self-esteem of the individual it is built on the basis of educational pedagogy.

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